

CONDUCTANCE OF SALTS IN NON-AQUEOUS SOLVENTS. PART II. CONDUCTANCE OF SALTS IN ETHYLPHENYLETHANOLAMINE

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Conductivities of a number of electrolytes, e. g., tetraethylammonium chloride, tetramethylammonium picrate, ethylamine picrate, ethylamine hydrochloride, nitrophenol, sodium, benzamide and sodium picrate, were determined under different experimental conditions using ethylphenylethanolamine as a solvent. The results presented in this paper show a great contrast to those in triethanolamine as a solvent (Part I of this series). The $\kappa c - \sqrt{c}$ curves are much steeper and cannot be trusted to give even approximate values of λ_{∞} . These curves show minima. After the minimum the conductivity rises sharply towards higher concentration. In the case of tetraethylammonium chloride, which was studied in a wide range of concentration, in addition to a minimum, a maximum occurs. It has been found in all cases that the portion of the curve beyond the minimum towards greater dilution has a slope of $-\frac{1}{2}$, which shows that the mass action law holds good between ions and ion-pairs, thus :

The object of the present investigation was to study the electrical conductance of solutions of uni-univalent electrolytes in ethylphenylethanolamine as a solvent. Ethylphenylethanolamine (I), should behave as an alcohol as well as a base. It has a fairly high viscosity but has a low dielectric constant.

The following electrolytes have been studied: (a) tetraethylammonium chloride, (b) tetramethylammonium picrate, (c) ethylamine picrate, (d) ethylamine hydrochloride, (e) *p*-nitrophenol, (f) sodium, (g) benzamide and (h) sodium picrate.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The experimental procedure was the same as in Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 24, 1).

The dielectric constant of ethylphenylethanolamine was measured by using an apparatus used by Nagamani and Jatkar (*J. Ind. Inst. Sci.*, 1941, 24A, 81). The dielectric constant was found to be 8.55 at 25°.

The viscosity of ethylphenylethanolamine was measured by both Ostwald and Redwood methods and was found to be 0.526 poises.

Preparation and Purification of materials.—Ethylphenylethanolamine supplied by the Carbide and Carbon Chemical Corporation was distilled under reduced pressure. The middle fraction of the distillate was dried over fused potassium hydroxide and was redistilled twice. This gave a very faintly yellowish liquid of sp. gr. 1.04. As the specific conductivity was considerably lower than 1×10^{-9} , it could not be accurately measured in our apparatus. The specific conductivity being very low, the solvent correction was negligible and so it was not applied.

Tetraethylammonium chloride, ethylamine hydrochloride and sodium derivative were prepared as stated in Part I (*loc. cit.*). The picrates were prepared by adding a

hot solution of picric acid to the hot solution of tetramethylammonium chloride and ethylamine hydrochloride. The crystals, separated on cooling, were washed with 95% alcohol and recrystallised several times from water-alcohol mixtures.

Pure nitrophenol was recrystallised from xylene and dried at 120°. Sodium picrate was prepared from 'A. R.' sodium hydroxide and picric acid and was purified by repeated crystallisations. Benzamide was recrystallised three times from water-alcohol mixtures.

The solvent and all the electrolytes were perfectly dried and preserved in a vacuum desiccator.

The results are recorded in Tables I to V. In the following tables, c is the concentration in gram-equivalents per litre. κ is the specific conductivity and λ_c , the equivalent conductivity. In Table V are summarised the results for electrolytes which are extremely weak. Their conductivities at lower concentrations are too low to be measured with any degree of accuracy.

TABLE I

Electrolyte = Et_4NClO_4 , Temp. = 25°.

Temp = 25°C					
$c.10^3$	$\lambda_c.10^2$	$c.10^3$	$\lambda_c.10^2$	$c.10^3$	$\lambda_c.10^2$
1.424	48.51	65.88	33.44	478.37	52.11
5.431	27.99	127.7	44.49	602.7	52.16
18.42	19.51	309.1	50.89	823.7	49.76
37.99	25.34	326.0	52.72	1075.0	42.83

TABLE II

TABLE III

TABLE IV

$\text{Me}_4\text{N-picrate}$, Temp. = 25°.		$\text{EtNH}_2\text{-picrate}$, Temp. = 25°.		$\text{EtNH}_2\text{-HCl}$, Temp. = 25°.	
$c.10^3$	$\lambda_c.10^2$	$c.10^3$	$\lambda_c.10^2$	$c.10^3$	$\lambda_c.10^2$
2.956	17.35	0.9294	25.93	26.98	2.159
10.35	12.77	2.905	15.08	97.86	1.980
22.25	11.48	7.435	9.705	291.0	3.115
31.46	10.92	15.48	10.43	616.0	4.584
41.30	10.71	28.60	6.133		
		44.32	9.998		

TABLE V

Temp. = 25°

Electrolyte.	c .	κ .	λ_c .	Electrolyte.	c .	κ .	λ_c .
p -Nitrophenol	5.0×10^{-2}	1.335×10^{-7}	2.67×10^{-5}	Benzamide	1.46×10^{-1}	1.569×10^{-7}	1.07×10^{-3}
	2.0×10^{-1}	6.929×10^{-7}	3.464×10^{-5}	Na picrate	1.52×10^{-3}	1.112×10^{-7}	7.3×10^{-3}
Na derivative					8.480×10^{-3}	2.463×10^{-7}	2.9×10^{-3}
EtN—Ph	3.0×10^{-2}	1.962×10^{-7}	6.54×10^{-5}				
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{ONa}$							

DISCUSSION

The results recorded above show a great contrast to those in triethanolamine as a solvent. The $\lambda_c - \sqrt{c}$ curves are much steeper and cannot be trusted to

give even approximate values of λ_{∞} . These curves show minima. All the electrolytes behave as weak electrolytes.

FIG. 1

Curves I—IV refer respectively to Et_4NClO_4 , Me_6N picrate, EtNH_2 picrate and EtNH_2HCl .

In the case of solvents of high dielectric constant, the departure from the simple Ostwald's dilution law can be satisfactorily explained by taking into consideration the effect of the ion-atmosphere. But when the dielectric constant is lowered, this ion-atmosphere effect becomes smaller and smaller, while the effect due to ion-association increases. Kraus and Fuoss (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 21) have pointed out that in the dielectric constant range between 10 and 20, it is necessary to take into account the equilibrium between free ions and ion-pairs.

This accounts for the rapid falling away of the equivalent conductance below values required by the Debye-Hückel-Onsager slope and for the linearity of the $\log \lambda_c - \log c$ plots. In solvents of still lower dielectric constant ($D < 10$), an equilibrium between free ions and ion-pairs giving rise to triple ions, must be considered :

This equilibrium will have an increasing influence as the dielectric constant is lowered. This accounts for the deviation of the $\log \lambda_c$ — $\log c$ curves from linearity in the dilute solutions and for the occurrence of the conductance minimum at higher concentrations.

The application of the law of mass action to this equilibrium between ions and ion-pairs (i) above, when the degree of dissociation is small in comparison with unity, i.e. when it is represented fairly accurately by λ_c/λ_0 , shows

$$\kappa = \frac{c\gamma^2}{1-\gamma} = \frac{c\gamma^2}{1} = c(\lambda_c/\lambda_0)^2.$$

From this it is clear that $\frac{d \log \lambda}{d \log c} = -\frac{1}{2}$. Thus, if the mass action law holds good between ions and ion-pairs, a plot of $\log \lambda$ against $\log c$ should have a slope of $-1/2$. This has been observed by Fuoss *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 21, 476, 1019, 2387; 1935, 57, 2604; 1940, 62, 506, 2238; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1934, 30, 67; *Chem. Rev.*, 1935, 17, 27) in a number of solvents. It can be seen from Fig. 1 that all the four electrolytes studied in ethylphenylethanolamine conform to this. The dotted lines which have the slope ($-1/2$) are almost parallel to the portion of the curve beyond the minimum towards greater dilution.

Minima are observed in all cases. After the minimum the conductivity rises sharply towards higher concentration.

In the case of tetraethylammonium chlorate, which was studied in a wide range of concentration, in addition to a minima, a maximum occurs. Walden has observed the same phenomenon in a number of solvents and states that a maximum generally occurs at approximately one normal. The maximum observed here is approximately at 0.6 *N*.

Kraus and Fuoss (*loc. cit.*) have derived equations from which the mass action constant can be theoretically calculated and a curve can be drawn theoretically to represent λ_c — $\sqrt{c}$ relations. These equations have not been applied in this part as (a) extrapolated values of λ_0 in this case are at best gross approximation, (b) the critical concentration, c_0 for ethylphenylethanolamine is 1.96×10^{-4} , which means that even the lowest concentrations used in the investigation are more than a hundred times of c_0 .

At these concentrations, the association effects may become more complex, aggregates of higher order than ion-pairs and triple ions must be considered :

These highly complicated association processes determine the course of nearly all the measurable properties of solutions in non-polar media.

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